

Synthesis and characterization of a novel mesoporous Mn-organophosphate molecular sieve

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Abstract : A novel mesoporous Mn-organophosphate was synthesized for the first time. It is characterized by several physicochemical techniques. Small angle X-ray diffraction analysis shows the first peak in 2.5° with 39 \AA pore width. Elemental analysis shows that the composition is $[(C_{12}H_{23}N)_3PO]^{40}Mn$. Scanning electron microscopic picture shows the flag morphology with $1-15 \mu m$ particle size. Thermogravimetry/Differential thermal analysis shows almost 80% exothermic weight loss. Nitrogen adsorption isotherm shows type III with $300 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$ BET surface area. Fourier transform Infrared spectroscopic analysis shows that the framework vibrations are comparable to other well known silica mesoporous materials. Electron spin resonance spectroscopic analysis shows the absence of hyperfine splitting indicates the presence of Mn^{3+} species. Ultraviolet-visible spectroscopic analysis shows that most of the Mn is in tetrahedral co-ordination beside small square pyramidal species. A plausible synthesis mechanism also proposed.

Keywords : Mesoporous, Mn-organophosphate, characterization.

Introduction

Mesoporous materials are popular due to their high surface area and unique morphology¹⁻¹⁰. The known variety of mesoporous materials are few, namely MCM-41, MCM-48 and SBA-15. The main draw back in these materials synthesis is their prolonged crystallization, low yield and high cost of reagents. There are several efforts were made in this direction to solve these problems. One among them was to synthesis organophosphate molecular sieve synthesis. They are prepared in short time, high yield and low cost. Beside they are similar to pure inorganic molecular sieves in many properties. Pure organophosphate molecular sieves are not suitable for redox type catalyzed reactions. To prepare redox catalyst, a metal oxide has to be either supported or incorporated inside the structure. As the supported metal oxides is leachable to liquid phase oxidation reactions. It is necessary to prepare metal incorporated molecular sieves. There are several metal incorporated¹¹⁻³⁵ molecular sieves are reported in literature. But there is no report on organophosphates. In this study we have synthesized a manganese incorporated mesoporous organophosphate for the first time. Their characterization was analyzed in detail.

Experimental

In a typical procedure to synthesis mesoporous Mn-organophosphate, the manganese acetate (P/Mn = 40, Aldrich, USA) was dissolved in orthophosphoric acid (85%, s.d.fine, India). To this mixture, 1 : 4 molar ratio of dodecylamine (98%, Aldrich, USA) was added and stirred well. A pink solid was resulted. The ground solid was dried at 80°C for 12 h. The resulting solid was subjected to various physicochemical characterizations.

The samples synthesized during the course of the work under different conditions were analyzed for qualitative phase identification by X-ray powder diffraction (Rigaku, Model D/MAX III YC, Japan, Ni filtered $\text{Cu-K}\alpha$ radiation, $\lambda = 1.5404 \text{ \AA}$). The morphology of the organophosphate was investigated using a scanning electron microscope (JEOL, JSM 5200). Simultaneous Thermogravimetry/Differential thermal analysis of the crystalline phases was performed on an automatic derivatograph (Setaram TG-DTA 92). The adsorption and desorption measurements were carried out using an Autosorb-1 instrument. The Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy was recorded in the diffuse reflectance mode using a 300 : 1 ratio sample in KBr (Nicolet 60SXB). Electron spin reso-

nance spectra of the as-synthesized Mn-organophosphate was obtained using Bruker ER 2000 spectrometer. The spectra were recorded at room temperature as well as at liquid nitrogen temperature. The spectra were recorded (with a mid range of 4000 G) in the scan range of 0 to 8000 gauss. The magnetic field strength was 9.74 GHz. The Ultraviolet-visible diffuse reflectance spectra were recorded using a Pye Unicem (SP-8-100) spectrometer in the 200–800 nm regions.

Results and discussion

The X-ray diffraction pattern of the Mn-organophosphate (Fig. 1) shows the peaks at 2.6 (54%), 3.8 (46%),

Fig. 1. Low angle X-ray diffraction pattern of mesoporous Mn-organophosphate molecular sieve.

5.3 (29%), 7.7 (100%) and 8.0 (71%). The appearance of peaks at low angle region in equal distance shows that the Mn-organophosphate is mesoporous lamellar type. The X-ray diffraction pattern is stable up to 200 °C. From the interplanar distance (d) analysis, the pore openings are calculated as 3.9 nm (39 Å)³⁶. Elemental analysis shows that the Mn-organophosphate has composition, $[(\text{CH}_3(\text{CH}_2)_{11}\text{NH})_3\text{PO}]^{40}\text{Mn}$.

Scanning electron micrograph of mesoporous Mn-organophosphate (Fig. 2a) shows that the particle size is not uniform (1–15 μm), however the shape is almost similar (flag shape). It is not soluble in aqueous or non-aqueous media. Presence of manganese plays a major role in it. Transmission electron micrograph of mesoporous Mn-organophosphate (Fig. 2b) shows a regular fringe for hexagonal framework. The well define fringe also shows its crystallinity.

The Thermogravimetry/Differential thermal analysis

(a)

(b)

Fig. 2. (a) Scanning electron micrograph and (b) transmission electron micrograph of mesoporous Mn-organophosphate molecular sieve.

of mesoporous Mn-organophosphate (Fig. 3) loses the total weight exothermically at 25–750 °C (80%). Unlike pure organophosphate (Figure is not shown) the Mn containing organophosphate loses the total weight at lower temperature. It may be due to the metal catalyses the oxidative decomposition of organics.

The nitrogen adsorption isotherms of Mn-organophosphate is of type III³⁷ (Fig. 4). The surface area is 300 m²/g and pore width is 40 Å. These results were taken after the materials were activated at 100 °C before measurement. If the material was activated at room temperature, no adsorption was taken place. Normally molecular sieves are activated at 400 °C in vacuum to remove the volatile impurities. The X-ray diffraction pattern of mesoporous Mn-organophosphate is reproducible even after its thermal treatment up to 200 °C. As we know, the X-ray diffraction reproducibility is essential for better nitrogen adsorption, so we have activated the sample under vacuum at 100 °C.

Fig. 3. Thermogravimetry (A)/Differential thermal analysis (B) curves of mesoporous Mn-organophosphate molecular sieve.

Fig. 4. Nitrogen adsorption isotherm curves of mesoporous Mn-organophosphate molecular sieve.

The Fourier transform infrared spectrum of as-synthesized mesoporous Mn-organophosphate shows (Fig. 5) a similar spectrum to other mesoporous molecu-

times higher than the room temperature pattern. Further, even though the source manganese is in Mn^{2+} state, when react with acid it is getting oxidized to Mn^{3+} . Besides for

Fig. 5. Fourier transform infrared spectrum of mesoporous Mn-organophosphate molecular sieve.

lar sieves. However there are slight changes in intensities. There was peak observed for Mn-O-P vibrations at 960 cm^{-1} band. Electron spin resonance spectrum of mesoporous Mn-organophosphate shows (Fig. 6) a single peak

a stable framework, manganese should be in Mn^{3+} . A week Mn^{2+} hyperfine splitting was also noticed.

Fig. 6. Electron spin resonance spectroscopic analysis of mesoporous Mn-organophosphate molecular sieve.

Fig. 7 shows the Ultraviolet-visible spectra of

Fig. 7. Ultraviolet-visible spectroscopic analysis of mesoporous Mn-organophosphate molecular sieve.

for Mn^{3+} oxidation state. It is noted that the Mn^{2+} is having six hyperfine splitting in ESR ($I = 5/2$)³⁸. At liquid nitrogen temperature the peaks intensity is four

mesoporous Mn-organophosphate. There is a small peak at 300 nm is due to the presence of tetrahedrally coordinated Mn or P species³⁸. Another peak at 415 nm is due to square pyramidal species. In Mn-organophosphate, only the tetrahedrally co-ordinated manganese is expected. However due to partial hydration, the square pyramidal species is appeared.

Scheme 1 shows a plausible mechanism for mesoporous

Scheme 1. A plausible mechanism for mesoporous Mn-organophosphate molecular sieve synthesis (A = *n*-dodecylamine, B = orthophosphoric acid, C = manganese acetate and D = Mn-organophosphate).

Mn-organophosphate synthesis. Orthophosphoric acid has three hydroxyl groups. This three hydroxyl can be easily reacting with three amine group. Being a Lewis acid, Mn is reacted with amine (Lewis base). The structural stoichiometry prevents manganese phosphate formation. The similarity of oxygen with nitrogen creates organophosphate structure similar to zeolites. The need for two hydrogen in organic amine supports this proposal. The organophosphate structure is neutral by presence of alternate P⁵⁺ and P³⁺ ions. The Mn³⁺ ions replace P³⁺ species to form stoichiometric structure.

Conclusions :

A novel mesoporous Mn-organophosphate was synthesized for the first time. It is characterized by several physicochemical techniques. Small angle X-ray diffraction analysis shows the first peak at 2.5° for mesoporosity. Elemental analysis shows that the composition is [(C₁₂H₂₃N)₃PO]⁴⁰Mn. Scanning electron microscopic picture shows the flag morphology with 1–15 μm particle size. Thermogravimetry/Differential thermal analysis shows almost 80% exothermic weight loss. Nitrogen adsorption isotherm shows it is of type III with 300 m²/g surface area. Fourier transform infrared spectroscopic analysis shows that the framework vibrations are compa-

able to other well known silica mesoporous materials. Electron spin resonance spectroscopic analysis shows the absence of hyperfine splitting indicates the presence of Mn³⁺ species. Ultraviolet-visible spectroscopic analysis shows the most of Mn is in tetrahedral co-ordination beside small square pyramidal species. A plausible mechanism of the reaction was also proposed.

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